

Speculation on the Maxwell-Boltzmann $\exp(-e_i/T)$ From the View of Conservation of Momentum

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In previous notes, we speculated that the key ideas leading to $\exp(-e_i/T)$ are present in the Newtonian mechanics of a single two body elastic collision. In particular, we noted that given an initial e_1 and e_2 , one may have various e_i, e_j outcomes such that $e_1 + e_2 = e_i + e_j$. We suggested that in general one does not have enough details to predict which e_i, e_j pair will be produced and argued for introducing a probability scheme such that $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_1)p(e_2)$ ((1)). For a single particle collision, such a probability might not seem to have much meaning (except in a quantum mechanical scheme not discussed here), but for an ideal gas which has many such collisions, there is a natural interpretation of $p(e_i)$, namely the probability to have a particle with energy e_i . Thus, we argue that probability introduced into a single elastic scattering interaction in Newtonian mechanics governs the probability scheme in an ideal gas.

Here, we try to consider how one would develop this idea starting with the notion of momentum conservation alone. We argue that one may consider a moving frame with two single particles side by side (held by a spring) which then creates $-p$ and p (momentum) in the rest frame. The absolute value of work is the same for both particles and momentum is equal and opposite. If the velocity of the frame is v_{cm} , then in the rest frame one has $m(v + v_{cm})$ (vector) and $m(-v + v_{cm})$. We argue that for any v_{cm} , the work done creating v and $-v$ has the same magnitude and so should be linked with the same probability. We ask: How can one describe this and consistently deal with different v_{cm} vectors? We suggest that taking the dot product of $v + v_{cm}$ achieves this goal as: $v \cdot v + v_{cm} \cdot v_{cm} + 2 v \cdot v_{cm} + v \cdot v + v_{cm} \cdot v_{cm} - 2 v \cdot v_{cm} = 2 v \cdot v + 2 v_{cm} \cdot v_{cm}$. In other words, v and v_{cm} are treated in the same way (as they should as an argument of probability) and $v \cdot v$ stands as a number representing part of a probability weight. In order for a sum to occur, one must map into an AND probability situation so number power $\{(v + v_{cm}) \cdot (v + v_{cm})\}$ seems to be the probability form to use because if $v \cdot v$ is the weight for all cases in which work is done to create a v or $-v$ in a rest frame, v_{cm} , being a velocity, must be treated in the same way. This in turn leads to a probability of $\exp(-C v \cdot v)$ if one wishes probability to decline with magnitude of v .

Newtonian Energy Approach to $\exp(-e_i/T)$, the Maxwell-Boltzmann Factor

In previous notes, we have argued that the Maxwell-Boltzmann factor $\exp(-e_i/T)$ arises from Newtonian considerations of a single elastic collision. Given that the collision is elastic, we focused solely on energy and argued that one may have:

$$E_1 + e_2 = e_i + e_j \text{ for a given } e_1, e_2, \text{ i.e. many } e_i, e_j \text{ pairs ((2))}$$

The question then is: Which e_i, e_j pair will emerge? We argued that in general one does not have enough information to answer this question and that there is thus probability already in the Newtonian elastic collision. We suggest that:

$$p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_1)p(e_2) \text{ or } p(e_i) = \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((3))$$

A free particle is normally not associated with a probability. In another note, we argued that one may capture this idea by using $\exp(-i C e_i)$ and then argued that one should really have $\exp(-i e_i t)$ and $\exp(i p \cdot r)$ (i.e. free particle quantum mechanics), but this is a topic not considered here. Rather, we note that even though one does not really have a usual (real valued) probability linked with $p(e_i)$ for a free particle in a Newtonian elastic collision, the same is not the case for a gas.

In an ideal gas one does have such a real probability, namely $p(e_i)$, the probability to have a particle with energy (kinetic) e_i (if not potential $V(x)$ is present). We argue that Newtonian two body elastic collisions occur in such an ideal gas and so ((3)) must be respected. Thus, the Newtonian collision probability feature actually determines the Maxwell-Boltzmann factor $\exp(-e_i/T)$ according to the above argument. We have, however, ignored momentum in the above discussion and ask: Can one come to the same conclusions simply using momentum considerations?

Momentum Consideration in Obtaining $\exp(-e_i/T)$

We start with the scenario of two equal mass particles joined by a coiled spring and held in place by a fastener. If the fastener is released, each particle obtains the same magnitude of momentum, but in opposite directions. We use rest mass $m_0=1$ and nonrelativistic considerations. The work is equal and opposite. We argue that each such particle with v (velocity vector) and $-v$ pair may be associated with different frames moving with constant v_{cm} (where the v_{cm} vector may take on all values). Regardless of v_{cm} , the work done producing v and $-v$ is the same and there should exist a feature of probability which recognizes this. At the same, whatever feature recognizes v or $-v$ (i.e. function of the vector v), must recognize v_{cm} in the same way because it is also a velocity. We suggest that given that v and $-v$ (vectors) should have the same probability feature, i.e. it cannot depend on sign. Thus, we propose:

$$(v+v_{cm}) \cdot (v+v_{cm}) + (-v + v_{cm}) \cdot (-v+v_{cm}) = 2 v \cdot v + 2 v_{cm} \cdot v_{cm} \quad ((4))$$

In other words, one picks out the $v \cdot v$ probability feature for v and $-v$ and v_{cm} is treated in exactly the same manner as v or $-v$. The question, however, is why should one add $(v+v_{cm}) \cdot (v+v_{cm})$ and $(-v+v_{cm}) \cdot (-v+v_{cm})$ be added. We suggested that one is considering an AND probability situation, i.e. v vector and $-v$ vector. This suggests a product $p((v+v_{cm}) \cdot (v+v_{cm})) p((-v+v_{cm}) \cdot (-v+v_{cm}))$. In order for a product to yield a sum of variables as in ((4)), one should have a base number to the power of ((4)), or:

$$\exp(-C (v+v_{cm}) \cdot (v+v_{cm})) \text{ so that the probability drops with rising } v+v_{cm} \text{ magnitude } ((5))$$

Thus, without even knowing about kinetic energy, one may derive ((5)). We now consider conservation issues.

Conservation of Momentum and Energy

We take conservation of momentum as a given which means that in the above discussion, if v_1 and v_2 are the initial velocities ($m_0=1$), then:

$$v_1 + v_2 = v + v_{cm} + -v + v_{cm} \text{ or } v_1 + v_2 = 2v_{cm} \quad ((5))$$

Considering:

$$\exp(-C v_1 \cdot v_1) \exp(-C v_2 \cdot v_2) \text{ versus } \exp(-C 2 v \cdot v + C 2 v_{cm} \cdot v_{cm}) \quad ((6))$$

In ((6)), $v_{cm} = (v_1 + v_2)/2$ so $v \cdot v$ and $v_{cm} \cdot v_{cm}$ are fixed. The catch is, however, that:

$v_1 \cdot v_1 + v_2 \cdot v_2$ may be matched with various sets of v_i, v_j vectors, such that:

$$v_1 \cdot v_1 + v_2 \cdot v_2 = v_i \cdot v_i + v_j \cdot v_j \quad ((7))$$

There are many values of v_i and v_j which satisfy ((7)), but one must ensure that momentum is also conserved. Nevertheless, if momentum is conserved, then one sees that there is a conserved value in the problem, namely $v_1 \cdot v_1 + v_2 \cdot v_2$. Thus, the idea of conservation of energy seems to emerge from a probabilistic description of the problem, it seems. Such a viewpoint suggests that any $v_i \cdot v_i$ and $v_j \cdot v_j$ pairs which add to $v_1 \cdot v_1 + v_2 \cdot v_2$ are acceptable and so the original Newtonian probability of an elastic collision emerges.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in a previous note we tried to argue that the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution $\exp(-e_i/T)$ emerges from Newtonian considerations of single elastic scattering interaction e_1 with e_2 because one does not know which e_i, e_j pair emerges if $e_1 + e_2 = e_i + e_j$. Given this lack of information, we suggest that one assumes that each e_i, e_j pair has the same product probability $p(e_i)p(e_j)$. Now there is no real value $p(e_i)$ for a free particle, but there is for a particle in an ideal gas. Thus, one may suggest that the Newtonian elastic scattering probability governs the Maxwell-Boltzmann result $\exp(-e_i/T)$.

Here we try to obtain the same result, by only considering momentum. We examine two particles joined by a fastened spring which achieve v and $-v$ (velocity vectors, $m_0=1$) after the spring is released. We argue that one may view this picture as a rest frame linked with many different v_{cm} vectors and that any probability associated with $-v$ and v should be the same and also carry the same weight regardless of v_{cm} . Furthermore, whatever function of v vector linked to probability that emerges, the same function must apply to v_{cm} because it is also a velocity. We suggest that $(v + v_{cm}) \cdot (v + v_{cm})$ and $(-v + v_{cm}) \cdot (-v + v_{cm})$ are the appropriate forms, but only if considered through a $p(v + v_{cm}) * p(-v + v_{cm})$ (i.e. an AND) scenario which suggests that probability should be proportional to $\exp(-C \text{ velocity} \cdot \text{velocity})$. Equal AND probabilities

in a problem, i.e $\exp(-C \mathbf{v}_1 \cdot \mathbf{v}_1) \exp(-C \mathbf{v}_2 \cdot \mathbf{v}_2) = \exp(-C \mathbf{v}_3 \cdot \mathbf{v}_3) \exp(-C \mathbf{v}_4 \cdot \mathbf{v}_4)$ suggests a conserved quantity in the problem (which turns out to be kinetic energy).